

Original Research Article

Social Support Pointers and Social Adjustment of Students with Hearing Impairment in Cameroon

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Abstract

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Social support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment constitute one of the socially constructed research niches grossly neglected by researchers particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa. Social support was operationalised in this study as emotional, financial; material supports. The social adjustment pathways of hearing-impaired students remain problematic as they battle through socially, culturally and educationally constructed impediments. The correlational survey research design was used and the samples of 19 students with hearing impairment were involved in the study. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The descriptive statistical tools used were frequency count, percentages and multiple responses set which aimed at calculating the summary of findings for each variable. To test the hypotheses of the study, the Spearman rho test was used because the data for the variables were not normally distributed based on the statistics of the test of normality assumption trend of the data. Findings indicated that there was a significant and relatively strong relationship between emotional support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment ($P < 0.001$, $r = 0.431^{**}$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R = 0.431^{**}$) implied that students with hearing impairment were more likely to be experience high social adjustment when they adequately received emotional support from their loved ones. Also, findings showed that there was a significant relationship between financial support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment ($P = 0.009$, $r = 0.261^{**}$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R = 0.261^{**}$) implies that students with hearing impairment were more likely to be experience high social adjustment when they adequately received financial support from their loved ones. Similarly, further analysis showed that there was a very significant relationship between material support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment ($P = 0.010$, $r = 0.256$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R = 0.256$) implied that students with hearing impairment were more likely to be experience high social adjustment when they adequately received material support from their loved ones. Conclusively, findings showed that social support has an effect on social adjustment of students with hearing impairment in the Buea Sub Division. It was recommended that teachers and parents and community should support and spend more time to listen and show love to students with hearing impairment. This will help the feel belong and loved which will enhance the psychological wellbeing and positive social adjustment in social situation.

Keywords: Buea Sub Division, Hearing Impairment, Pointers, Social adjustment, Social Support, Students

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a vital role in the development of human capital and is linked to an individual's adjustment and opportunities for better living. Education ensures the

acquisition of knowledge and skills that enable individuals to increase their productivity and improve their quality of life (Battle and Lewis, 2002). Institutions where education

takes place provide an important place for students to act out their competencies and enjoy their relationships. The social experiences in schools leave enduring imprints on the social life of the students (Bursuch and Asher, 1996). Students with impairment in general and hearing-impaired in particular face numerous difficulties in school life and related scenarios (Moeller et al., 2007).

Development of social skills, peer relationships, and academic performance of the students is extremely influenced by hearing impairment (Moeller, 2007). In order to cope with such hardships, the school system plays a central role because such students need special attention and care. Educational stakeholders play a vital role in developing the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment. The degree to which students are able to establish and maintain satisfactory interpersonal relationships, gain peer acceptance, establish and maintain friendships, and terminate negative or pernicious interpersonal relationships defines social competence and predicts adequate long-term psychological and social adjustment (Gresham et al., 2001).

Individual's circle of friends can support his or her development of social competence by (1) learning how to interact with people in a manner that he can accept and respond to positively, (2) helping to teach him social skills, and (3) letting other people know that they are individual's friends and that developed many positive qualities. Nobody develops social adjustment in isolation. This paper explores empirically, contextual dynamics of social support on the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment.

Tracing the context of social support efforts

The development of deaf community in Cameroon is tied to the founding of deaf schools (Ceuppens and Geschie, 2005). The first deaf school was not established until 1972, the Cameroonian deaf community is young. The first deaf school graduates are now in their forties and fifties. Although further research is needed, the narratives of deaf community members throw a first light on the development of Cameroon Sign Language (CSL). The first deaf school, founded by French missionaries in Yaounde (now the national capital), had an oral educational philosophy. Initially sign language was not used in the school (Ceuppens and Geschie, 2005). Deaf children apparently developed their own sign communication in the playground, which differed from the gestures used in their home environment and villages.

It also appears that this emergent sign language got little room to grow. In 1979 Andrew Foster, a deaf African American missionary, founded a school in Kumba and introduced American Sign Language (ASL). Interview with noncongenitally deafened deaf adults who worked in the school Foster's time and a handbook of the language

of instruction for individuals who received teacher training in Foster's centre in Nigeria, however, revealed that an English-language sign system rather than ASL was used (Fleischer, 2007)

Most Cameroonian deaf adults in the areas of research are using an ASL influenced variant of CSL; in limited areas there is a first generation of young deaf people using a CSL variant that is influenced by LSF). Both cases of linguistic colonialism have been inspired by ideological and political arguments. These arguments, as well as the influence of dominant spoken languages (French, English, Pidgin) and the influence of gestures, must be taken into account if one is to gain a full understanding of the linguistic mosaic of signed language(s) in Cameroon and its sociolinguistic context. Linguistic research is needed to ascertain whether 'Cameroon Sign language' is a national language with regional variations or whether different sign languages are used in Cameroon. Such a determination will be helpful to efforts to win recognition of CSL and to protect Cameroonian indigenous signs (UNICEF, 2009).

All deaf schools in Cameroon are private and, since school fees must be paid, many deaf children do not have access to education. Secondary deaf education is only just beginning - two deaf schools recently established a programme for secondary education. Other deaf schools provide some support to deaf students who are mainstreamed. There are no professional interpreters in Cameroon, there is no training programme for sign language interpreters, and the government does not provide interpreting services (Fleischer, 2007).

Consequently, deaf students often drop out. In 2008 a programmed of Special Needs Education was founded at the University of Buea. It currently hosts the UNESCO Chair in Special Needs Education. The Cameroon National Association of the Deaf (CANAD) and members of the academic community in Cameroon have expressed a need for further capacity building in the areas of research and teaching in sign language, deaf studies and deaf education. There is currently no academic training for teachers of deaf children in Cameroon. This probably also explains why deaf adults speak critically about the limited education they received in the deaf schools (Yuh and Shey, 2008)

Poverty and the marginalised position of deaf people in Cameroonian society make it very hard to get the means to pay a dowry and to gain the family consent necessary to marry a deaf spouse. In the past 10-15 years deaf adults have seen few changes, and they feel neglected by the national government and by the CANAD. There seem to be scant prospects for the future. The raw and energetic anger of the Cameroonian deaf adults I met in Douala affected me deeply (Fisiy, 1998).

Since independence, Cameroon has gone through a lot of development socially. One of them is the educational system where students are equipped with a wholesome personality and high leadership quality to be

capable of dealing with present and future challenges. Education has grown to develop rapidly to cater for the demands and needs of the developing nation with the main aim of training high quality and professional students. The students are equipped with a wholesome personality and high leadership quality to be capable of dealing with present and future challenges. As far as academic performance is concerned, it is important to look at the roles played by the social support. It is an aspect that should be reviewed since it is described as both a buffer against life stressors as well as an agent promoting health and wellness (Dollete et al., 2004).

In the Cameroon context, the dramatic changes in education and impact on the student experience are beginning to receive steady attention. Issues related to transition and experiences of students suggest that students, especially those in form one, face an adjustment problem in this transitional period. Building a firm understanding of student experience is important in order to understand the effects of social support on social adjustment of students with hearing impairment. Students believe that learning is not totally an individual process or achieved exclusively in a classroom, but it happens through communication and exchange within or outside academic trajectory. So therefore, they need to be motivated, encouraged, and supported by their parents, friends, teachers and the school administration playing its part, in order to help them to be socially adjusted to their feet for studies and their environment.

A review of the present Situation on Special Needs Education in Cameroon (Yuh and Shey, 2008). suggested that children with severe language, hearing, learning or behavior problems were excluded from the public education system. Categories of special educational needs were not included in the legislation (Hegarty, 1995). The review also discussed the lack of administrative structures that deal with specific issues of special education. The government takes an active role in the supervision of private agencies that provide services and education for individuals with special education needs. As of 2003, only 10 institutions (segregated schools for more significant disabilities such as visual impairments, multiple disabilities (mostly physical), deaf/hard of hearing, and behavioral disorders) existed in Cameroon that serve the needs of individuals with disabilities; out of the ten, only two are government institutions (Yuh and Shey, 2008). The lack of specification in the legislation for the education of students with special education needs leads to the general belief that individuals with disabilities are to be educated in a segregated environment. Many students with special education needs do not have access to basic education in Cameroon (Yuh and Shey, 2008). Titanji (2008) argued that Cameroon needs to move from passing the laws on Education for All in an inclusive environment to the actual implementation. This move will involve all stakeholders in education in Cameroon:

parents, teachers, principals and head teachers, and policy makers.

Social support first emerged in the mid-1970s and has been one of the most intensely studied psychosocial factors in health. Although research involving allied concepts like social network, social capital, social ties, and social integration was abandoned prior to the 1970s, it was not until the mid-1970s that studies on social support as a distinct construct came into existence. This concept was first used in the mental health literature. Scientific interest in the importance of social support first emerged in the 1970s when health researchers developed an interest in the health consequences of being socially integrated (Stroebe and Stroebe, 1996). Recent scientific interest in social support derives largely from lectures by distinguished physician epidemiologists with strong psychosocial interest and expertise (Cassel, 1976; Cobb, 1976). It focuses on, and contributes to the subjective level of wellbeing, contentment and satisfaction in the past; hope and optimism for the future and flow and happiness in the present (Vazquez et al., 2009).

Through this method, it is predicted that in the new century, positive psychology will allow individuals, societies and communities to flourish (Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). For this reason, research literature in recent years has had more emphasis on well-being than on disorder and dysfunction (Huppert, 2009). The center of mind during the late 1800s, Durkheim first examined the importance of social ties, defined as family, friends, and organized religion. Durkheim is credited with being the "father of sociology" and published a number of sociological articles (Vaux, 1988). He discovered a link between decreased social ties with increased rates of suicide. He also linked social ties to what is now referred to as social support. In addition, social support appears to have taken the place of the following terms: "caring, friendship, community cohesion, and unconditional regard" (Tilden, 1999). Social network was a term also used before social support (Weinert, 2003). Some refer to the informal groups of persons surrounding each of us as social networks and social support (Gottlieb and Bergen, 2010). All of these terms indicate a wide umbrella under which research on social support has taken place.

The education of students with special education needs has been a concern to the international community since the 1994 United Nations Salamanca statement and framework for action on special needs education (UNESCO, 1994). World nations committed to provide access for students with special needs to be educated with their peers. As a member of the United Nations, Cameroon has passed laws in relation to the education of students with disabilities. The education of individuals with special education needs was introduced in Cameroon in 1975 with the creation of the Ministry of Social Affairs (MSA), which was responsible for the well-being of individuals with disabilities (Yuh and Shey,

2008). Cameroon Law No. 83/13, Article 3, of July 1983, provided for the needs and protection of individuals with disabilities with three major provisions: integration of children in ordinary schools, admission in special classes, and admission into specialized institutions (Protection of Disabled Persons, 2003). Understanding teacher perceptions towards students with disabilities continues to be one way to assist with making progress in educating students with disabilities

Gurung (2006) noted that social support refers to the experience being valued, respected, cared about, and loved by others who are present in one's life. It may come from different sources such as family, friends, teachers, community, or any social groups to which one is affiliated. Social support can come in the form of tangible assistance provided by others when needed which includes appraisal of different situations, effective coping strategies, and emotional support. Social support is an element that can help individuals to reduce the amount of stress experienced as well as to help individuals cope better in dealing with stressful situations. Several studies indicated that supportive contacts correlate negatively with symptoms and psychological disorders such as stress, depression and other psychiatric disorder, and positively correlate with physical and mental health.

There are different criteria to determine the extent of a person's social adjustment achieved a good measure: Real appearance through the attitudes and real behavior. If the social behavior of individuals in accordance with the standards of a group or meet the expectations of the group, then the individual will be accepted as a member of the group. It can be seen from self-actualization, which is a process to be ourselves and be able to develop the properties and potential; interpersonal relationship skills, and be able to open himself to others, are willing to accept and provide knowledge or information to others (Somantri, 2007)

Individuals will be able to adjust well socially if they are able to show good behavior towards others, participate in social participation, as well as participate in group activities. It can be realized by participating in social activities in the community, show empathy and mutual respect. Individuals can adapt well to a variety of groups, both peer groups and groups of adults. It can be realized in cooperation with a group whose members support each other to achieve good results; carry out the responsibilities of the well, sharing, and motivated to do good and loyalty in friendship. Individuals should be able to adapt to the social, able to feel satisfied with their social contacts and able to participate in various social situations. It can be seen through the self-confidence, self-discipline and life meaningful and purposeful (Schneiders, 1964).

According to Feldinald and Feldinal (2006), adjustment is the continuous process of satisfying one's desire, mastery of the environment and sense of being at peace with oneself. Thus, it implies that adjustment is the

ability to select appropriate and effective measures so as to meet demands of the environment while maintaining a healthy attitude towards the circumstance. Spincer and Jeffrey (1995) reported that students who fail to adjust face a torrid time, and may commit suicide, which is reportedly the second leading cause of deaths in Western colleges and universities.

Social support is one of the most important protective factors for students with hearing impairment (Tao et al., 2000). This is because social support includes social resources that individuals perceive to be available or that are actually offered to them which could help protect against psychological problems. According to Teoh and Rose (2001), lower level of social support is one of the predictors of psychological and adjustment problems. It is associated with higher levels of depression, anxiety, attention problems, thought problems, social problems, somatic complaints, and lower self-esteem. According to Friedlander et al. (2007), students with hearing impairment who perceive that their social resources increase away have lower level of adjustment problems. This shows that the impact of a stressful situation for example can be decreased when students have good social support. Advice and encouragement from sources of support may also increase the likelihood that an individual will rely on active problem solving and information seeking. These may assist students in dealing with various stressors in the environment and facilitate a positive adjustment process.

The supportive actions provided by social support are thought to buffer the impact of stress by increasing the effectiveness of coping efforts, which in turn decrease distress among students with hearing impairment (Lakey and Cohen, 2000). For example, receiving emotional support and companionship may encourage effective adaptation among students with hearing impairment in facing and coping with uncontrollable events. According to Rawson, Bloomer and Kendall (1994) students with hearing impairment with good social support tend to have lower scores on stress compared to the students with low social support. According to them coping behavior and social support structures moderate the effects of stress among students with hearing impairments in their academic life.

Tolsdorf (1976) describes emotional support as assistance in the form of encouragement, personal warmth, and love. Jacobson (1986) described emotional support as a behavior that fosters feelings of comfort and leads an individual to believe that he or she is admired, respected, and loved, and that others are available to provide care as well as security. Thus, emotional support conveys the expressions of care and concern that serve to elevate a person's sense of own value and adequacy (Gottlieb, 1983). An expression such as telling someone, "You mean so much to me", meets an individual's emotional or affective needs.

Providing an emotional support can have a particularly

powerful impact on the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment who may be academically at risk. Consider, for example, students with hearing impairment who move from school to school due to problems associated with low self-esteem and lack of social acceptance (Reitzug and Patterson, 1998). Helping these students with hearing impairment recognize that they are members of a supportive community makes it easier for them to adapt and concentrate on learning (Reitzug and Patterson, 1998). Thus, it is reasonable to consider school efforts to provide emotional support for students with hearing impairment especially those most at risk of failure a key strategy in addressing the academic gap and raising overall student performance. There is a clear theoretical base for connecting students' with hearing impairment feelings of emotional security and their ability to focus on learning. Maslow's hierarchy of human needs suggests that students who have their needs for safety, belonging, and self-esteem met as well as their basic physiological needs possess an important foundation for building knowledge.

Material support refers to provision of goods and services that help to solve practical problems (Jacobson, 1986). Material support can be regarded as the provision of tangible support that aims to enhance students with hearing impairment social adjustment and learning (Tennant et al., 2015). Material resources include food stuff, textbooks, charts, maps, audiovisual and electronic instructional materials such as radio, tape recorder, television and video tape recorder. Other category of material resources consist of paper supplies and writing materials such as pens, eraser, exercise books, crayon, chalk, drawing books, notebooks, pencil, ruler, slate, workbooks and soon (Atkinson, 2000).

Adeogun (2001) discovered a very strong positive significant relationship between materials resources and student social adjustment with those of hearing impairment. According to Adeogun, children with hearing impairment in schools endowed with more materials are easily adjusted and thus, perform better than schools that are less endowed. Mwiria (1985) also supports that students performance is affected by the quality and quantity of teaching and learning materials. The author noted that institutions with adequate facilities such as textbooks stand a better chance of performing well in examinations than poorly equipped ones. Therefore, poor performance could be attributed to inadequate teaching and learning materials and equipment.

Hill et al., (2004) also argued that financial support for students does not only affect the academic performance of the child with hearing impairment, but also makes it impossible for the child to compete with his counterpart from high financial status under the same academic environment as this goes a long way to hinder their social adjustment. Furthermore, Smith, Fagan and Ulvund (2002) asserted that a significant predictor of intellectual performance of a child at age of 8 years, included

financial support. Other researchers had posited that parental financial support to students could affect school children by bringing about flexibility to adjustment to the different school schedules (Guerin et al., 2001). In another finding, Oni (2007) and Omoegun (2007) had averred that there is significant difference between the rates of deviant behaviour among students from high and low socio-economic status.

Theoretical framework

Theoretically, the study employs three theoretical frameworks drawn from the Vygotsky (1978) theory of social constructivism, Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory (1943) and the ecological systems theory of Urie Bronfenbrenner (1979). The social learning theory propounded by Bandura (1977) posits that people learn from one another, via observation, imitation and modeling. The focus of this theory is observable behaviour acquired, maintained, modified and gotten rid of through the contingencies that underlie the social environment. The theory assumes that behaviour of children comes as a result of children observing the people around them behaving in various ways. For instance, in society people are surrounded by many models, such as parents, guardians and friends. These models provide examples of masculine and feminine behaviour. Significant in this relationship between the child and the person modeling its behaviour is that behaviour displayed by parents and other close relatives is likely to be replicated in the child. In short, the amount of experience and exposure with which the behaviour is modeled may affect the likelihood to which the behaviour may be replicated. The interaction, therefore, among moral behaviour, moral cognition and environmental factors plays a role in social adjustment. This kind of interaction and support system guided this study.

Maslow theory (1943) posits that each person has a hierarchy of needs that must be satisfied, ranging from physiological requirements to love, esteem and finally self-actualization. Therefore, for the home and school to maintain discipline, certain basic requirements such as food and shelter need to be provided to the children. Failure to meet the basic needs may lead to deviant behaviour. Besides, when children come to school, they come with the needs or reasons that need to be satisfied. It is the needs that motivate the pupils to behave accordingly so that they achieve social adjustment. The kind of needs that influence an individual's behavior and adjustment guided this study as well.

Also, Bronfenbrenner (1979) ecological systems theory of development presents an evolving systemic process of interaction between the human organism and the environment. Bronfenbrenner posits that there is a dynamic relationship between individual functioning and the social environment in shaping child development. The

theory explains the extent to which home environment occurs in relation with the social milieu for them to adapt to the environment. Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory is of significance to this study because it contextualizes human development and shows a variety of influence on the development of students in different support systems and settings. This theory enables us to also understand that we are living in a supportive society and it is important to understand the support system and its influence on the social adjustment of students.

Vygotsky (1978) social constructivism theory stresses the fundamental role of social interaction in the development of cognition, as he believed strongly that the community plays a central role in the process of making meaning. Vygotsky, (1978) argued that learning is a necessary and universal aspect of the process of developing culturally organized, specifically human psychological function. Vygotsky believed that young children are curious and actively involved in their own learning and the discovery and development of new understandings and Vygotsky placed more emphasis on social contributions to the process of learning. According to Vygotsky (1978), much important learning by the child occurs through social interaction with a skillful tutor. The tutor may model behaviors and provide verbal instructions for the child. Vygotsky refers to this as cooperative or collaborative dialogue. In order to gain an understanding of Vygotsky's theory, one must understand two of the main principles of Vygotsky's work: the More Knowledgeable Other (MKO) and the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). This theory situates the study in that it focuses on the interactions that a child is engaged in within the society and it is through these interactions that the child can perceive as being loved or not. If a child is able to feel that he/she is being loved by friends, parents and teachers he/she will have a stable mind and will be less disturbed thinking about why he is not loved which enhance social adjustment.

Emotional support and student's social adjustment

Wilson et al., (1999) studied the influence of gender and emotional versus instrumental support on cardiovascular reactivity in African-American adolescents with hearing impairment. Research suggests that females with hearing impairment seek out, prefer, and are more receptive to emotional support (encouragement), and that males seek out, prefer, and are more receptive to instrumental support (problem-solving). Thus, we hypothesized that boys would show lower Blood Pressure (BP) reactivity in response to instrumental than emotional or no support, and that girls would show lower BP reactivity in response to emotional than instrumental or no support. Forty-eight healthy African-American adolescents (50% males) participated in a role play conflict task and were randomized to receive either emotional, instrumental, or

no support (presence only) from a confederate. Boys showed lower Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) reactivity in the instrumental than in the emotional or no support conditions and lower recovery SBP as compared to boys in the emotional or no support conditions. A similar pattern of results was demonstrated for Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) reactivity. Girls, however, did not demonstrate lower BP reactivity in response to emotional as compared to instrumental support. These findings suggest that instrumental and emotional support differentially influence cardiovascular (CV) reactivity in African-American boys versus girls.

Morelli, Lee, Arnn and Zaki (2015) investigated on emotional and Instrumental Support Provision Interact to Predict Well-being Participants consisted of 49 same-gender pairs (25 pairs of males, 24 pairs of females; total $N = 98$; mean age = 19.41) with 36% Caucasian, 14% Hispanic/Latino, 14% Black/African American, 12% East Asian, 3% South Asian, 2% Pacific Islander, 1% Middle Eastern, 5% Other/Undisclosed, and 13% Mixed Race. Data was analysed using Multilevel Confirmatory Factor Analysis (MCFA) to examine the underlying *structure* of support provision. Also, they implemented Multilevel Modeling (MLM) procedures to examine relationships between each factor of support provision and well-being (Hox, 2002), while accounting for the hierarchical data structure (that is, daily ratings nested within participant, and participants nested within dyads). Findings revealed that providers' emotional support (for example, empathy) and instrumental support represent distinct dimensions of support provision, replicating prior work. Crucially, emotional support, but not instrumental support, consistently predicted provider well-being. These two dimensions also interacted, such that instrumental support enhanced well-being of both providers and recipients, but only when providers were emotionally engaged while providing support. These findings illuminate the nature of support provision and suggest targets for interventions to enhance well-being.

Adekunle (2018) conducted a study on emotional Support and Personality Traits as Predictors of social adjustment of Postpartum student with hearing impairment in Oyo State, Nigeria. Using survey design, 258 students with hearing impairment (Mean age = 29.05) who's postpartum is between 0-3months were purposively and accidentally sampled in two selected schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics. The results showed that emotional support and personality traits jointly predicted the four subscales of social adjustment respectively as indicated: 3.6% of Somatic Symptoms, 4.7% of Anxiety and Insomnia, 3.5% of social dysfunctions and 6.9% of Severe Depression. Of the emotional support subscales, only perceived emotional support was found to independently and significantly predict Social Dysfunctions. Younger students with hearing impairment

significantly scored higher on somatic symptoms (mean score = 11.24) than old students (mean score = 10.180); $t = 2.040$; $df = 256$; $p < .05$; Also, young students with hearing impairment significantly reported higher level of severe depression (mean score = 12.034) than old students with hearing impairment (mean score = 10.693); $t = 2.368$; $df = 256$; $p < .05$. Students with hearing impairment with low formal education reported higher levels of somatic symptoms, anxiety and insomnia and severe depression than those with high school and tertiary education.

Agu (2010) carried out a study titled "relationship between emotional patterns and students with hearing impairment academic adjustment schools in Enugu education zone. The design for the study was correlation survey design. The instrument for data collection was question. The sample of the study was 59 students. The researcher analyzed the data using Pearson Product moment correlation coefficient. The result of the study revealed that emotional patterns relate to students with hearing impairment academic adjustment. They study further revealed that emotion is an integral aspect of learning indicating that different emotional construct are correlated with effective classroom learning and adjustment

Financial support and the student's social adjustment

Mofoka (2016) conducted a study on the effects of tertiary students' financial problems on academic performance of person with hearing impairment: the case of Motheo Technical Vocational Education and Training in Bloemfontein. This study investigated financial problems faced by students with hearing impairment at Motheo Technical Vocational Education and Training and aims to come up with support interventions to enhance academic performance in order to positively contribute to the overall student experience and throughput rates. Using a qualitative approach in collecting data, the study tried to find out the experiences of students with hearing impairment and effects of financial problems on academic performance. Social capital theory and social justice framework provided the theoretical underpinning for the study. Social capital theory helped the researcher to find out students' experiences and how they cope. Social justice focuses on policy, national and institutional efforts in eliminating the identified financial problems faced by disadvantaged students at tertiary institutions. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with a sample of 10 students and the head of the department of business studies. A further sample of 36 purposively selected students was drawn for a questionnaire survey to triangulate findings from the personal interviews. Results of the study show that due to financial problems, the students encounter problems such as inability to cope

with the high standards of studying as well as difficulty in paying fees and accessing basic needs. Data gathered from the interviews and surveys insinuates that financial problems have adverse effects on students' academic performance, but contrary to the study's assumptions, and review of secondary data, no correlation could be found between financial need and poor academic performance or outright failure. In conclusion, it is recommended that, more policy research is needed to come-up with alternative policy solutions and to make adjustments to existing measures intended to cater for the needs of students with hearing impairment from disadvantaged backgrounds.

Szkody and McKinney (2020) studied financial, stress and social support as moderators between stress and physical and psychological quality of life. The current study examined the expansion of the original stress-buffering hypothesis to include primary or secondary appraisal in an emerging adult population ($N = 854$) on physical and psychological health outcomes. The additional moderating effects of gender also were examined. Perceived social support (by the Multi-dimensional Survey of Perceived Social Support) significantly buffered the effects of financial stress from negative events (by the Risky Behaviour and Stressful Events Scale) on physical and psychological health (by the World Health Organizations Quality of Life Instrument) for females only. Neither primary nor secondary appraisal (by the Stress Appraisal Measure) acted as additional buffers for male or females. Social support may be a more salient buffer for females. Reappraisal mechanisms may have another role in the buffering pathways.

Lin (2016) Examined the Effects of Financial Aid on Student with hearing impairment Persistence in Taiwanese Higher Education. The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of financial aid policies on student with hearing impairment persistence between the first and second year at a private four-year postsecondary institution in Taiwan. A two-phase sequential research design was employed with priority was given to the quantitative data-structural equation modeling (SEM). While the conceptual framework of this study was drawn from multiple research antecedents in relation to student with hearing impairment persistence the major perspective guiding it was based on St. John's (1992) analysis of the research. Overall, the greatest effects on persistence were the measures of high school academic performance, followed by campus work, academic integration, social aspiration for attending college, financial aid, and parental supports, while neither parental educational attainments, faculty-student interactions, the practical value for future employment, nor peer relations were associated with students' with hearing impairment decision to remain enrolled in college, results which merit further investigation. In sum, this study provides a necessary beginning step, more

institutional research is needed in Taiwan to improve policy makers' and institutional researchers' understanding of the complex interplay between student financial aid and college experiences in students with hearing impairment decisions to persist in college as well as to develop a longitudinal database to identify ways to increase student success.

Park et al. (2006) studied financial support, appraisals, and coping as predictors of depression in congestive heart failure patients. The aim of the present study was to expand on Holahan et al.'s model of social support and active coping as determinants of depression in individuals with cardiac illness. We examined social support, appraisals, and coping as subsequent predictors of depression in a sample of 163 community-dwelling individuals with diagnosed congestive heart failure patients. The results of structural equation analyses indicated that the satisfaction with social support and percentage of active coping employed were prospectively related to lower levels of depression, and that appraisals of one's illness as threatening were a strong predictor of higher levels of depression. These findings suggest that focusing on financial support and coping processes may be a useful avenue for alleviating depression in those living with congestive heart failure patients.

Material support and student's social adjustment

Tao (2000) conducted a study on material support and students with hearing impairment wellbeing. The researcher used survey design for the study. The sample for the study consists of 40 students with hearing impairment. The instrument used by the researcher for data collection was a structured likert type questionnaire. The researcher used weighted means in analyzing the data. Material support was found to be one of the most important protective factors for students with hearing impairment. This is because material support includes social resources that individuals perceive to be available or that are actually offered to them which could help protect against psychological problems. According to Teoh and Rose (2001), lower level of materials support is one of the predictors of psychological problems. It is associated with higher level of depression, anxiety, attention problems, thought problems, social problems, somatic complaints, and lower self esteem. These notions are supported by the study of Friedlander et al. (2007) on 128 first year undergraduate students. It was found that students who perceived that their material resources increased had lower level of psychological problems. This shows that the impact of a stressful situation for example can be decreased when students have good material support. Gifts and encouragement from sources of support may also increase the likelihood that an individual will rely on active problem solving and information seeking.

Kang (2013) conducted a study on Instrumental social support, material hardship, personal control and neglectful parenting. The purpose of this study was to test pathways from perceived instrumental social support to neglectful parenting with two mediating variables-material hardship and personal control. I used a subsample of mothers ($n = 2910$) who participated in the Fragile Families and Child Wellbeing study (FFCW) from the birth of their children through age 5. The model fits the data well and the findings supported the proposed pathways among variables. Perceived instrumental social support decreased material hardship and increased personal control. Decreased material hardship and increased personal control in turn decreased neglectful parenting. Decreased material hardship also increased personal control. The study's findings contribute to the design and evaluation of social support prevention programs for child neglect.

Williamson and LeFevre (1992) studied tangible assistance: a simple measure of social support predicts pregnancy outcome. The association between tangible assistance, a single-item measure of social support, and serious perinatal complications was prospectively measured in 548 rural pregnant women. Those 38 women who reported no or one reliable helper in the third trimester (low tangible assistance) had a higher rate of poor outcomes (at least one of the following: neonatal death, transfer to neonatal intensive care unit, birth weight less than 2500 g or 5-min Apgar score less than 7) than those with 2 or more helpers (13.2% vs. 5.7%, $p = 0.08$). All of the increase in poor outcomes occurred in women with high socio demographic risk (at least one of the following: age less than 18, no male partner, or less than high school education). In this subgroup of 121 women, the difference in poor perinatal outcomes was striking (28.6% vs. 7.6%, $p = 0.03$). The association between tangible assistance and poor outcome remained after controlling for biomedical risk. A simple question about the availability of supportive companions may be clinically useful

Wong et al. (2018) studied Teacher support in learning: Instrumental and appraisal support in relation to math achievement with student of hearing impairment. This study explored the extent to which teachers' instrumental (i.e., tangible aid to promote learning) and appraisal support (i.e., teacher feedback) enhanced students with hearing impairment achievement in mathematics. Participants included 950 fifteen-year-old Canadian students with hearing impairment who participated in the 2012 Programme for International Student Assessment. Based on students' reports, results from hierarchical regression analyses showed that instrumental support and teacher feedback respectively positively and negatively predicted math achievement. Further, teacher feedback made an additional contribution to math achievement over and above instrumental support. Findings suggest that different

types of teacher support might differ in their efficacy in promoting math achievement.

Statement of the Problem

For students with hearing impairment to succeed to be socially adjusted, they need to come from a supportive families and society. From observation, students with hearing impairment are mostly coming from unsupported families and are discriminated by the society. Some of the families don't care about their needs and wellbeing. Some of the hearing-impaired students face a number of challenges, including developing social support network, keeping up with different educational demands, and manage interpersonal and societal demands which are part of college experience. The process of adjustment to the college environment can be frustrating and overwhelming for students with hearing impairments, leading to emotional maladjustment, depression, and poor academic outcomes. Most students with hearing impairment suffer from transitional adjustments, problem of adaptation, fear of embarrassment, inferiority complex in interactions and some avoid class participation. Some students with hearing impairment get hungry in school and do not have what to eat. Some fear public speaking because of the concern that others will notice they have a disability. They experience it with tensed anxiety which may influence their adjustment.

Anxiety may exacerbate feelings of hopelessness or negative expectancies toward oneself and the future which have been associated with negative outcomes such as violence, depression, school problems, substance abuse, risky sexual behaviours, and accidental injury. With such hardships, it is not surprising that students with hearing impairment in Buea Sub Division often exhibit poorer outcomes on many objective measures of adjustment such as isolation, low self-esteem, inability to adapt and resist, introvert, and poor preparation toward adulthood. It is against this back drop that the study seeks to investigate the influence of social support on the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment in Buea Sub-Division.

Objective of the study

The main objective of this is to find out the effect of social support on the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment in the Buea Municipality

Specific objectives

- To investigate the effect of emotional support on the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

- To find out the effect of financial support on the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment
- To examine the effect of material support on the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between emotional support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between financial support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between material support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

The study made use of correlational survey research design, in which a large population is studied by collecting and analyzing information from only sample of the population considered to be representative of the whole and in turn generalizing the results obtained on the entire population. The correlational survey research design was used because the researcher was interested in looking at the relation between social support and the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of all the students with hearing impairment in the Buea Sub Division. The target population of the study consists of all the students in the Buea school for the Deaf (Record office, 2020/2021) [Table 1](#)

The accessible population of this study comprised of 20 students in the Buea School for the Deaf [Table 2](#)

Sample population

The sample size was made up of 19 students with hearing impairment. The sample was determined through Krejcie and Morgan (1970) model of determining sample size for research activities. This model states that the accessible population of 20 needs the sample of 19 respondents. [Table 3](#)

The sample size from each class was gotten based on the total population of the accessible population. To get the sample size of 5 from the form one, the accessible population of form one (5) was divided by the overall

Table 1. Distribution of the Target Population

Class	Population
Form one	6
Form two	0
Form three	4
Form four	4
Form five	12
Total	26

Source: Record office, 2020/2021 of Buea school for the deaf

Table 2. Distribution of the Accessible Population

Class	Accessible population
Form one	5
Form three	3
Form four	3
Form five	9
Total	20

Table 3. Distribution of the Sample Population

Class	Accessible population	Sample size
Form one	5	5
Form three	3	3
Form four	3	3
Form five	9	8
Total	20	19

population of the school and multiplied by the overall sample size (19). These same procedures was done for form three, form four and form five that gave sample sizes of 3, 3 and 8 respectively.

FINDINGS

Findings showed that a majority of them 16 (84.2%) accepted that they do not feel tense when interacting with strangers. Findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 17 (89.5%) accepted that they easily make friends in school. Also, findings showed that a majority of the respondents 17 (89.5%) accepted that they feel disturbed when faced with financial difficulties. To elucidate, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 15 (78.9%) accepted that they easily interact with friends and feel confident about their self.

Table 4

Findings also showed that all the respondents 19 (100%) accepted that feel happy when their siblings show concern toward them. Findings also showed that while 6 (31.6%) of the respondents accepted that they easily

adapt to new situation, a majority of them 13 (68.4%) disagreed. Also, findings showed that while 10 (52.6%) of the respondents accepted that they do not suffer from mood swings, a significant proportion of them 9 (47.4%) do. Findings also showed that while 12 (63.2%) of the respondents accepted that they easily overcome their difficult moments, 7 (36.8%) of them are unable. Finally, findings also showed that a majority of the students with hearing impairment 18 (94.7%) are not comfortable in the present of others. In aggregate, findings showed that 59.5% of the students with hearing impairment have high social adjustment while 40.5% of them are low in their social adjustment. **Table 5**

Statistically, comparing the students with hearing impairment social adjustment by demographic characteristics, findings showed that they do not significantly differ by the demographic characteristics ($P > 0.05$). By form, findings showed that those in form one (61.3%), form three (54.3%) and four (65.0%) of also most the same proportion are high in their social adjustment. By gender, findings also showed that female (60.9%) are slightly higher in their social adjustment than male (57.3%). Finally, by age range, findings also

Table 4. Social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Items	Stretched			Collapsed		
	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	SA/A	D/SD
I don't feel tense when I interact with strangers	9 (47.4%)	7 (36.8%)	3 (15.8%)	0 (0.0%)	16 (84.2%)	3 (15.8%)
I can easily adapt to new situations	3 (15.8%)	3 (15.8%)	12 (63.2%)	1 (5.3%)	6 (31.6%)	13 (68.4%)
I easily make friends in school	3 (15.8%)	14 (73.7%)	2 (10.5%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (89.5%)	2 (10.5%)
*I feel disturbed when faced with financial difficulties	1 (5.3%)	16 (84.2%)	2 (10.5%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (89.5%)	2 (10.5%)
I easily interact with my mates	1 (5.3%)	14 (73.7%)	2 (10.5%)	2 (10.5%)	15 (78.9%)	4 (21.1%)
I am not suffering from mood swings	1 (5.3%)	9 (47.4%)	8 (42.1%)	1 (5.3%)	10 (52.6%)	9 (47.4%)
I can easily overcome my difficult moments	2 (10.5%)	10 (52.6%)	5 (26.3%)	2 (10.5%)	12 (63.2%)	7 (36.8%)
I always feel confident about myself	1 (5.3%)	14 (73.7%)	4 (21.1%)	0 (0.0%)	15 (78.9%)	4 (21.1%)
I feel happy when my siblings show me concern	16 (84.2%)	3 (15.8%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	19 (100%)	0 (0.0%)
I feel comfortable in the present of others	1 (5.3%)	0 (0.0%)	14 (73.7%)	4 (21.1%)	1 (5.3%)	18 (94.7%)
Multiple Response Set (MRS)	37 (19.5%)	76 (40.0%)	66 (34.7%)	11 (5.8%)	113 (59.5%)	77 (40.5%)

*Items with coding reversed during the calculation of MRS

Table 5. Comparing respondents' social adjustment by demographic characteristics

Demographic characteristics		Social adjustment		Total based on MRS	Chi-square test (χ^2)
		High	Low		
Form	Form one	n	49	31	$\chi^2=0.98$ df=2 P=0.589
		%	61.3%	38.8%	
	Form three	n	38	32	
		%	54.3%	45.7%	
	Form four	n	26	14	
		%	65.0%	35.0%	
Gender	Male	n	46	34	$\chi^2=1.67$ df=1 P=0.345
		%	57.5%	42.5%	
	Female	n	67	43	
		%	60.9%	39.1%	
Age	15-20 years	n	88	52	$\chi^2=5.89$ df=1 P=0.005
		%	62.9%	37.1%	
	21-26 years	n	25	25	
		%	50.0%	50.0%	

showed that those of age 15-20 (62.9%) are higher in their social adjustment than those 21-26 (50.0%).

Question One: How can emotional support affect the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment?

Based on students with hearing impairment opinion on

emotional support, findings showed that all the respondents 19 (100%) accepted that their teachers guide them whenever they are disturbing and that they received feedback from the teachers about their mood. Findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 17 (89.5%) accepted that their friends always encouraged them in times of difficulties. Also, findings showed that a majority of the respondents 11 (57.9%) accepted that their teachers correct them in a

Table 6. Respondents' opinion on emotional support

Items	Stretched				Collapsed	
	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	SA/A	D/SD
My teachers guide me whenever I am disturb	16 (84.2%)	3 (15.8%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	19 (100%)	0 (0.0%)
I get feedback from my teachers about my mode	14 (73.7%)	5 (26.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	19 (100%)	0 (0.0%)
My parents always ask of my problems	7 (36.8%)	3 (15.8%)	3 (15.8%)	6 (31.6%)	10 (52.6%)	9 (47.4%)
My friends always encouraged me in times of difficulties	14 (73.7%)	3 (15.8%)	2 (10.5%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (89.5%)	2 (10.5%)
When I make mistakes, my teachers in a pleasant and constructive way tells me how I can avoid such mistakes in the future	4 (21.1%)	7 (36.8%)	8 (42.1%)	0 (0.0%)	11 (57.9%)	8 (42.1%)
I have friends that i always share my feelings with	15 (78.9%)	2 (10.5%)	2 (10.5%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (89.5%)	2 (10.5%)
I have people who always think of me	10 (52.6%)	5 (26.3%)	3 (15.8%)	1 (5.3%)	15 (78.9%)	4 (21.1%)
My mate always finds faults in whatever I do	1 (5.3%)	5 (26.3%)	11 (57.9%)	2 (10.5%)	6 (31.6%)	13 (68.4%)
When I want to talk with my teachers, they give me the opportunity to do so	3 (15.8%)	11 (57.9%)	3 (15.8%)	2 (10.5%)	14 (73.7%)	5 (26.3%)
My family always called to ask of my wellbeing	0 (0.0%)	3 (15.8%)	14 (73.7%)	2 (10.5%)	3 (15.8%)	16 (84.2%)
Multiple Response Set (MRS)	84 (44.2%)	47 (24.7%)	46 (24.2%)	13 (6.8%)	131 (68.9%)	59 (31.1%)

constructive manner when they make mistakes. Furthermore, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 17 (89.5%) accepted that they have friends that they always share their worries with them. To elucidate, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 15 (78.9%) accepted that they have people who always think of them. Finally, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 14 (73.7%) accepted that their teachers always given them the opportunity when they want to talk to them. In overall, findings showed that a majority of the students with hearing impairment 68.9% accepted that they received adequate emotional support from loved ones while 31.1% of them do not. **Table 6**

Statistically, comparing the students with hearing impairment opinion on emotion support by demographic characteristics, findings showed that they do not significantly differ by the demographic characteristics ($P > 0.05$). By form, findings showed that those in form one (67.5%), form three and four (70.0%) of also most the same proportion accepted that they received adequate emotional support. By gender, findings also showed that female (72.7%) received emotional support more than male (63.8%). Finally, by age range, findings also

showed that those of age 15-20 (68.6%) and 21-26 (70%) of almost equal proportion accepted that they do receive adequate emotional support. **Table 7**

Testing of hypothesis one (H_0): There is no significant relationship between emotional support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Statistically, findings showed that there is a very significant and relatively strong relationship between emotional support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment ($P < 0.001$, far < 0.05). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R = 0.431$) implies that students with hearing impairment are more likely to be experience high social adjustment when they adequately received emotional support from their loved ones. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis that states that there is a significant relationship between emotional support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment was accepted. **Table 8**

Table 7. Comparing respondents' opinion on emotion support by demographic characteristics

Demographic characteristics		Emotional support		Total based on MRS	Chi-square test (χ^2)		
		Adequate	Inadequate				
Form	Form one	n	54	26	$\chi^2=0.54$ df=2 P=0.675		
		%	67.5%	32.5%			
	Form three	n	49	21			
		%	70.0%	30.0%			
	Form four	n	28	12			
		%	70.0%	30.0%			
Gender	Male	n	51	29	$\chi^2=2.96$ df=1 P=0.124		
		%	63.8%	36.3%			
	Female	n	80	30			
		%	72.7%	27.3%			
	Age	15-20 years	n	96		44	$\chi^2=0.25$ df=1 P=0.872
			%	68.6%		31.4%	
21-26 years		n	35	15			
		%	70.0%	30.0%			

Table 8. Relationship between emotional support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Test	Statistical parameters	Emotional support	Social adjustment of students with hearing impairment
Spearman's rho	R-value	1.000	.431**
	P-value	.	.000
	N	19	19

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 9. Respondents' opinion on emotional support

Items	Stretched			Collapsed		
	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	SA/A	D/SD
My parents always sent me money every month	2 (10.5%)	3 (15.8%)	11 (57.9%)	3 (15.8%)	5 (26.3%)	14 (73.7%)
I have all exercise and text books	0 (0.0%)	1 (5.3%)	16 (84.2%)	2 (10.5%)	1 (5.3%)	18 (94.7%)
I always buy all my handouts	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	15 (78.9%)	4 (21.1%)	0 (0.0%)	19 (100%)
I often eat want i like	0 (0.0%)	1 (5.3%)	16 (84.2%)	2 (10.5%)	1 (5.3%)	18 (94.7%)
My parents provide me with school fees on time	1 (5.3%)	1 (5.3%)	15 (78.9%)	2 (10.5%)	2 (10.5%)	17 (89.5%)
I always have credit to call my parents	1 (5.3%)	1 (5.3%)	15 (78.9%)	2 (10.5%)	2 (10.5%)	17 (89.5%)
My friend always give me money	1 (5.3%)	0 (0.0%)	16 (84.2%)	2 (10.5%)	1 (5.3%)	18 (94.7%)
My house rents are always paid on time	1 (5.3%)	0 (0.0%)	14 (73.7%)	4 (21.1%)	1 (5.3%)	18 (94.7%)
*I do have problems when it comes to money	1 (5.3%)	1 (5.3%)	14 (73.7%)	3 (15.8%)	2 (10.5%)	17 (89.5%)
I always pay taxi every day when going to school	1 (5.3%)	1 (5.3%)	15 (78.9%)	2 (10.5%)	2 (10.5%)	17 (89.5%)
Multiple Response Set (MRS)	10 (5.3%)	22 (11.6%)	134 (70.5%)	24 (12.6%)	32 (16.8%)	158 (83.2%)

*tems with coding reversed during the calculation of MRS

Table 10. Comparing respondents' opinion on financial support by demographic characteristics

Demographic characteristics			Financial support		Total based on MRS	Chi-square test (χ^2)
			Adequate	Inadequate		
Form	Form one	n	9	71	80	$\chi^2=2.45$ df=2 P=0.232
		%	11.3%	88.8%		
	Form three	n	18	52	70	
		%	25.7%	74.3%		
	Form four	n	5	35	40	
		%	12.5%	87.5%		
Gender	Male	n	10	70	80	$\chi^2=2.78$ df=1 P=0.211
		%	12.5%	87.5%		
	Female	n	22	88	110	
		%	20.0%	80.0%		
Age	15-20 years	n	17	123	140	$\chi^2=6.78$ df=1 P=0.011
		%	12.1%	87.9%		
	21-26 years	n	15	35	50	
		%	30.0%	70.0%		

Table 11. Relationship between financial support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Test	Statistical parameters	Financial support	Social adjustment of students with hearing impairment
Spearman's rho	R-value	1.000	.261**
	P-value	.	.009
	N	19	19

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Question two: How can financial support affect the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment?

Findings showed that a majority of them 14 (73.7%) disagreed that their parents always sent them money every month. Findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 18 (94.7%) disagreed that they have all exercise and text books. Also, findings showed that a majority of the respondents 18 (94.7%) disagreed that they often eat what they like. Findings also showed that all the respondents 19 (100%) disagreed they buy all their handouts. To elucidate, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 17 (89.5%) disagreed that their parents provide their school fees on time. Furthermore, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 18 (94.7%) disagreed that their parents always give them money and paid their rents on time. Finally, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 17 (89.5%) accepted that they have money problems and that they do not always go to school by taxi. In aggregate, findings showed that a majority of the students with hearing impairment 83.2% do not received adequate financial support from their loved ones while 16.8% of them do receive adequate financial support from their loved ones. [Table 9](#)

Statistically, comparing the students with hearing impairment opinion on financial support by demographic characteristics, findings showed that they do not

significantly differ by the demographic characteristics ($P > 0.05$). By form, findings showed that those in form one (88.8%), form three (74.3%) and four (87.5%) indicated that they received inadequate financial support. By gender, findings also showed that female received financial support more than male. Finally, by age range, findings also showed that those of age 15-20 received financial support less than those of 21-26. [Table 10](#)

Testing of hypothesis two (H_{02}): There is no significant relationship between financial support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Statistically, findings showed that there is a very significant relationship between financial support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment ($P = 0.009, < 0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R = 0.261^{**}$) implies that students with hearing impairment are more likely to be experience high social adjustment when they adequately received financial support from their loved ones. However, though the relationship is weak but significant ($P < 0.05$), the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis that states that there is a significant relationship between financial support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment was accepted. [Table 11](#)

Statistically, comparing the students' with hearing

Table 12. Comparing respondents' opinion on material support by demographic characteristics

Demographic characteristics		Material support		Total based on MRS	Chi-square test (χ^2)		
		Adequate	Inadequate				
Form	Form one	n	42	22	$\chi^2=5.67$ df=2 P=0.032		
		%	65.6%	34.4%			
	Form three	n	45	11			
		%	80.4%	19.6%			
	Form four	n	29	3			
		%	90.6%	9.4%			
Gender	Male	n	44	20	$\chi^2=7.87$ df=1 P=0.004		
		%	68.8%	31.3%			
	Female	n	72	16			
		%	81.8%	18.2%			
	Age	15-20 years	n	84		28	$\chi^2=1.90$ df=1 P=0.453
			%	75.0%		25.0%	
21-26 years		n	32	8			
		%	80.0%	20.0%			

Table 13. Relationship between material support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Test	Statistical parameters	Material support	Social adjustment of students with hearing impairment
Spearman's rho	R-value	1.000	.256**
	P-value	.	.010
	N	19	19

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

impairment opinion on material support by demographic characteristics, findings showed that those in form one (65.6%) received less material support compared to those in form three (80.4%) and form four (90.6%). In other words, material support for the students was found to increase with increase in class. By gender, findings also showed that female (81.8%) received material support more than male (68.8%). Finally, by age range, findings also showed that those of age 15-20 (75.0%) received material support less than those of 21-26 (80.0%). [Table 12](#)

Testing of hypothesis three (H_{03}): There is no significant relationship between material support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment

Statistically, findings showed that there is a very significant relationship between material support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment ($P = 0.010, < 0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R = 0.256^{**}$) implies that students with hearing impairment

are more likely to be experience high social adjustment when they adequately received material support from their loved ones. However though the relationship is weak but significant ($P < 0.05$), the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis that states that there is a significant relationship between material support and social adjustment of students with hearing impairment was accepted. [Table 13](#)

Based on the persons that are supportive in the life of those with hearing impairment to achieve their educational goals, findings showed that a majority of them 10 (52.6%) indicated their mother while 5 (26.3%) of them said their father. Based on the kind of support they provide, findings showed that they payment of fees was the most mentioned, followed by provision of basic needs and accommodation. Checking of their wellbeing was the least mentioned. [Table 14](#)

Implications of Findings to Special education

Findings revealed that social support was found to have an effect on students' with hearing impairment social

Table 14. Persons supportive in the life of those with hearing impairment to achieve their educational goals and the things they do

Persons supportive in the life of those with hearing impairment to achieve their educational goals			What do they do to make you feel that they are supportive?		
Persons	Frequency	Percentage		Frequency	Percentage
Mother	10	52.6	Pay fees	11	57.9
Father	5	26.3	Provide Basic needs	4	21.1
Brother, Sister	1	5.3	Provide me accommodation	3	15.8
Friend	1	5.3	Check my wellbeing	1	5.3
Uncle	1	5.3			
Aunty	1	5.3			
Total	19	100	Total	19a	100

adjustment. It decreases the use of harmful disengagement and increase coping strategies such as avoidance, withdrawal, and denial among students. Consequently, it can increase the use of beneficial engagement because individuals believe their social network includes someone who is willing to listen to them. This is supported by Gould (1999) who noted that children with hearing impairment adjust better in school when their parents are involved. Henderson, (cited in Gould, 1999) found that parents are involved in school in four ways. The first two are widely accepted: parents serve as teachers of their children at home and also serve as volunteers and supporters at school. The next two include parents becoming advocates for their children and decision-makers in school in such areas as school policy, hiring, and budget.

Again, this finding revealed that social support in terms of emotional, materials and financial support are the predictors of individual's adjustment. The combination of material and financial support has been associated with higher grades in schools and colleges. This is because availability of social support will reduce students' misconduct, psychological distress, and delinquency among students with hearing impairment of all social classes which would produce significant effect on students' academic achievement and adjustment. This is in line with Henderson and Berla's study (as cited in Bowen, 1999) who stated that students succeed in school when parents become involved by providing financial and material support in their children's education. This will lead to higher grades and test scores, better attendance and regularly completed assignments, fewer placements in special education and remedial classes, more positive attitudes and behaviour in school, higher graduation rates, and greater enrolment in secondary education. This finding is also in line with the view of Carter (2000) who stated that it is necessary to create an environment where children are safe and can easily succeed.

CONCLUSION

This paper on social support pointers and the social adjustment of students with hearing impairment have contextual relevance. With regard to the effects of emotional support and material support on social adjustment, it is important to note the types of stressors. According to Goldsmith (2004), the influence of social support varies according to the types of needs based on different stressors. Wilcox and Vernberg (1985) also argued that research dealing with social support should consider the recipients of the support as well as the types of problems they face. In other words, the effect of social support type on social adjustment depends both on respondents and their situations. In the current study, the effects of emotional and material support on social adjustment are also explained by respondents' characteristics.

While like all people, students are confronted with difficulties and thus need social support, their problems are primarily limited to school life, including issues related to academic goal orientation and social goal pursuits. It is rare for students to experience a wide range of adult problems, such as bankruptcy, divorce, or diseases like cancer. This specific respondent sample therefore influences the effects of social support type. For example, MacGeorge, Samter, and Gillihan's (2005) study concluded that emotional support and material support were substantive social support types that influenced how students with hearing impairment socially adjust. Consequently, for students, emotional support and material support are the most effective factors contributing to their development of resilience, more so than esteem support, network support, or tangible support.

Unlike emotional support and informational support, the other types of social support (i.e., esteem support, network support, and tangible support) were not significantly linked to resilience. This finding indicates that

not every type of social support has the same level of impact on social adjustment. The various types of social support need to be considered and the impacts of each assessed. Also, some researchers have focused on distinctions between the different types of social support and have explained their effects in a variety of contexts (e.g., MacGeorge, Samter, & Gilihan, 2005; Xu & Burleson, 2001). Therefore, it cannot simply be said that resilience is influenced by social support.

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